

Short history of ultrasonography

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Abstract

Untrasound is the basis of medical diagnosis. But when we would like to understand we have to back to history of USG. Its modern look and wide use for its continuous technological development. As a result, the diagnostic imaging equipment has become smaller, lighter, while improving the quality of the presented objections. Today's USG machine is a lightweight, mobile device. USG FAST machines are in the hands. Increasing the possibilities of using ultrasonography in medical diagnostics, especially in the case of diagnosing people in the trauma.

Key words: *Ultrasound, ultrasonography, USG, history, history of USG,*

Continuous technological development makes many medical devices smaller and lighter, without sacrificing image quality. A great example of this is the USG, which at first was big, heavy and stationary, today completely changed to conquer the world of emergency medicine. From large standing cabinets over time, he became a smaller and more mobile device, which increased the importance of ultrasound in diagnostics. [1] Today's modern ultrasonography even in the classic version is a device that makes it easy to mix it, while USG scan is a small lightweight camera in the palm of your hand.

Ryc.1 Ultrasound machine [2]

Ryc.2 USG FAST [3]

This minaturisation of the device allowed it to be used outside of fixed treatment centers, as exemplified by the use of FAST in emergency medicine. Medical resuscitation in many cases is extremely demanding and responsible. Every call for an ambulance can be a fight for health and even the life of the patient. This requires rescuers to quickly and accurately assess the condition and condition of the patient, and subsequent decisions should be made within a few seconds on the basis of available means and diagnostic methods. A particular situation is the state of immediate danger to life, in which even a second is extremely valuable, and every action has

consequences. Ultrasonography allows the medical team to properly assess the situation and implement a suitable treatment algorithm, while allowing the hospital to inform the patient of the actual condition. [4] This allows the hospital to prepare a team of specialists necessary for the survival of the patient. Ultrasonography alone is completely painless for the patient - pain only occurs in a few pathological conditions. USG is a study that allows you to evaluate the size and quality of organs, their location, and the pathological changes in your body. [5, 6] To better understand and fully utilize the capabilities of ultrasound devices, it is worthwhile to go back to the very beginning.

The history of modern equipment dates back to antiquity. It was in ancient Greece that they became interested in acoustics, and they were involved in Pythagoras and Aristotle, and they were the founders of the physical properties of sound and its characteristics. Many years people were fascinated with sound, and people learned to know about it. This led to the creation of the first ultrasonography in history. For example, in 1822, Daniel Colladen was able to estimate the velocity of a son's gravitational attraction by using a bell in the waters of Lake Beneson. The obtained results, ie 1435m / s, are not much different from those adopted today, today about 1500m / s. The next step was to discover Curie brothers piezoelectric effect, took place in 1880 and was a breakthrough in the research of supersonic and its properties. The experiments in the following years increased the knowledge of utrasonography, which was originally used in the Navy, served as a echolocation, but over time it dented itself as a diagnostic method in medicine. [5,7,8]

Ryc. 3 The phenomenon of echolocation on the example of a cave bat. [9]

Ultrasonographs were originally used in medicine for therapeutic purposes only, then in physiotherapy and rehabilitation, it was associated with a thermal effect. Despite the use of sound in medicine, research has not been stopped. Examples were neurosurgeons from

the Universities of Illinois and Ilow in the 1940s who used ultrasound to destroy basal ganglia in patients with Parkinson's disease, but this was only palliative treatment. At the same time, the Dussik brothers tried to locate brain tumors and ventricular system by ultrasound. They tried to achieve this by using pinned transducers on the opposite sides of the skull. Thanks to their work, the world has seen a great deal of ultrasonography as a diagnostic tool. It speaks to it: simplicity of execution, high accuracy, non-invasiveness, and the ability to see internal structures without invasive interference in the human body. Another breakthrough was the demonstration of the presence of gallstones by Ludwig, a Pennsylvania physician. His team, which continued the study, presented a two-dimensional ultrasound image, which allowed for their precise localization, without the need for surgery to open the patient's body, which was impossible until now.

In the post-war years where many new developments have taken place in the field of electronics, new piezoresistive materials have provided increased sensitivity, frequency range and efficiency, while reducing device depletion, allowing more frequent use of ultrasonography as a diagnostic tool. Scientists around the world have seen tremendous potential for ultrasonography, so they have been researching the next use of ultrasonography in medical diagnostics. Japanese scientists built the first camera for the presentation A-spot display on an iscoscope screen, then continued work on presentation B and two-dimensional grayscale imaging. [5, 10] Further research and development enabled the creation of an instrument that would allow one of the first presentation B to be presented to the public, and was created in Scotland in 1957 by Brown and Donald. It was used to diagnose in obstetrics and diagnose abdominal cavity as a method by which you can observe all changes occurring within the patient's body. Donald, initiated the use of ultrasonic flaw detectors for the detection of metal defects for the assessment of pelvic and abdominal tumors. His work has led to the development of our currently known two-dimensional ultrasound imaging in grayscale. Ultrasonography was first used in patients with multiple organ injuries in the late 1960s and early 1970s as a rapid and excellent diagnostic method. [5,7,11]

USG in the world

In Poland, its history starts in 1964 (conducted under the supervision of Prof. Leszek Filipczyński), in 1977 they resulted in the creation of the first ultrasonograph (with a pantograph arm). [5,7]

Ryc. 4 The first USG machine in the Poland[12]

Ultrasonographic studies in the 1970s were a novelty, which was a challenge for specialists wishing to fully exploit the potential of this method. The lack of textbooks in Polish has forced Polish specialists to self-improvement for better diagnostics. It was only after the summer that publications appeared, and training began to be made to fully utilize ultrasonography.

Not only in Poland but also in other countries the USG has reasarch. Researchers around the world have continually improved their technology and research techniques to maximize the potential of ultrasonography. Therefore, it is worth mentioning a few facts from history. In Germany in the 1970s ultrasound was indicated as an essential diagnostic tool in the case of injury and in emergency medicine. It was noted that ultrasound allows rapid and accurate diagnosis without interfering with the human body. However, it was only in 1988 that the USG was certified. This shows how ultrasound scanning is an extremely valuable diagnostic test. Also in Japan in 1980 USG was used for diagnosed injuries and politrauma.

In the mid 1980s, the USG became aware of the potential of ultrasound as a diagnostic tool. In the case of injuries it allowed us to diagnose quickly. The current DPL, ie diagnostic peritoneal lavage on the ultrasound. It was in the US that FAST was created. It was introduced in 1996 by Rozycki and his co-workers. Originally intended for rapid evaluation of patients after politrauma, however, over time it was also used in other cases. It was a quick way to diagnose patients. This resulted in the FAST protocol being incorporated in 1997 as part of the ITLS, the International Trauma Life Support. [13] Of course this did not mean stopping the development of the ultrasound. Continuous research and research from around the world have enabled the refinement of existing instruments and protocols for research. This resulted in the creation of the e-FAST protocol. [11,13,14] FAST is an extended FAST study. It covers the standard FAST test, plus a chest test. It is intended

to confirm the presence of fluid (blood) in the cage and the respiratory tract. This can be done in a very short time, which is extremely important in emergency medicine. We perform eFAST in 2 levels:

1. In the third and fourth intercostal spaces on the front wall of the chest.
2. In the third, fourth and fifth trimesters in the axillary line.

Rescue ultrasonography has undoubted advantages over other diagnostic tests. [7]

Conclusion:

Over the years, thanks to the work of many scientists, ultrasound technology has grown to be used today in medicine as a diagnostic and intervention tool, as well as in screening. Advancements in technology and continuous improvement of the software have improved the image quality and miniaturization of equipment, leading to more and better use of the imaging capabilities available.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.